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Optical Properties, Bandgap and Urbach Energy Determination of Ag Doped CdZnTe – PVA Nanocomposite

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Introduction: Nano sized semiconductors embedded in polymer composites attracts a great research interest due to the enhanced and tunable optical properties. Introduction of suitable metal nanoparticles like Cu^+ , Ag^+ , Mn^{2+} into the semiconductor polymer nanocomposite give rise to improved optical and structural properties. The dispersion of metal-semiconductor quantum dots in polymer matrices can give rise to much stabilized and handy hybrid materials quite suitable for tailored applications and development of sensors (1). Ternary CdZnTe alloy semiconductor quantum dots were much appreciated among the cadmium-based quantum dots due to high photostability, quantum yield and less toxicity (2). The polymer Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) is an environment friendly and biocompatible transparent material widely used as a good solute for multiphase nano systems. The present work optimizes the changes in linear optical constants, bandgap energy, urbach energy and fluorescent emissions of both CdZnTe-PVA and Ag: CdZnTe-PVA polymer nanocomposites.

Methods: The hybrid freestanding polyvinyl alcohol films embedded with ternary alloy CdZnTe and Ag: CdZnTe were synthesized by in-situ chemical method. The structural, optical and morphological characterizations of the polymer nanocomposites were done by techniques such as X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis, Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), UV-Visible and Fluorescence spectroscopy. The linear optical constants of the polymer nanocomposites obtained from the absorption and transmission spectra in the region 350 nm – 600 nm.

Results & Discussions: The X-Ray diffraction patterns of pure PVA shows semicrystalline nature and the crystal planes for CdZnTe indicates a cubical structure. The peaks of CdZnTe- PVA were less intense and broadened due to the polymer coating and quantum size effect of the nanocrystals. The TEM images show the formation of dopant clusters due to agglomeration. The band gap energy of the samples was estimated using Tauc method and the band gap for Ag doped sample was found to be lower than the undoped sample because of the introduction of defect states. The band gap tailing was established by calculating Urbach energy. The Urbach energy was found to be increase for Ag doped CdZnTe-PVA due to the increase in impurity level. The optical constants absorption coefficient (α), extinction coefficient (k), refractive index (n), real (ϵ_1) and imaginary (ϵ_2) part of dielectric constant and optical conductivity (σ_{opt}) were calculated. Ag doped CdZnTe-PVA shows enhanced values compare to the undoped CdZnTe-PVA. The samples CdZnTe – PVA and Ag: CdZnTe – PVA gives green fluorescence. The fluorescence spectrum of Ag doped samples showed a red shift and an increase in intensity.

Conclusions: The hybrid polymer nanocomposites, CdZnTe- PVA and Ag: CdZnTe- PVA shows excellent optical and fluorescence properties. The enhanced optical constants in Ag doped CdZnTe-PVA indicates, improved optical quality of the polymer nanocomposites. The Green- fluorescence and enhanced optical constants can be utilized in the fields of fluorescent probes, display systems and efficient optoelectronic devices.

Keywords: Hybrid polymer nanocomposite, CdZnTe quantum dots, Tauc plot, Urbach energy

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